

Complexes of Cobalt(III) with Violuric and Thiovioluric Acids. Synthesis and Characterisation

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Complexes of the type $\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{L})_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, where L=violuric acid (VA) or thiovioluric acid (TVA) have been synthesised and characterised. Their deprotonation equilibria in aqueous solution has been studied and it has been observed that they behave as triprotic acid giving the complex anions $[\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{L})_2(\text{HL})]^-$, $[\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{L})(\text{HL})_2]^{2-}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{HL})_3]^{3-}$, which have been isolated by selective precipitation and characterised.

COMPLEXATION reaction of cobalt(II) with violuric acid and thiovioluric acid in solution has been studied spectrophotometrically¹ and used for the selective determination²⁻⁶ of metal. It has been observed that cobalt(II) complexes are readily oxidised by atmospheric oxygen to cobalt(III) species, but their true nature even in solution has not been established. In the present paper we report the synthesis of complexes having general formula $\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{L})_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, where L=violuric or thiovioluric acid(I) and their characterisation by elemental and thermal analysis, conductivity and magnetic susceptibility measurements. These complexes behave as triprotic acid in aqueous solution giving the complex anions $[\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{L})_2(\text{HL})]^-$, $[\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{L})(\text{HL})_2]^{2-}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{HL})_3]^{3-}$. The deprotonation equilibria has been studied and acidity constants are determined. It has been observed that various equilibria overlap but by selective precipitation of various complex anions the compounds $\text{Cs}[\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{L})_2(\text{HL})] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{17})_3(\text{CH}_3)\text{N}]_2[\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{L})(\text{HL})_2]$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6][\text{Co}(\text{HL})_3] \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ have been isolated and characterised.

prepared by the method of Lal and Dutt⁷. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade.

Metal analysis of the complexes were made by standard gravimetric procedure⁸ and carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen analysis were carried out by CDRI, Lucknow. Study of deprotonation equilibria and determination of acidity constants have been made *pH* metrically at $25 \pm 2^\circ$ and ionic strength 0.5M of KCl, in nitrogen atmosphere with Beckmann Expandometric SS-2 model *pH* meter fitted with glass and calomel electrodes. Conductivity measurements have been performed with Philips conductivity bridge GM 4249 at $25 \pm 1^\circ$. Thermogravimetric analysis has been carried out in static air at a heating rate of $5^\circ/\text{min}$ on a Perkin-Elmer Thermobalance TGS-1. Magnetic susceptibilities of the complexes have been measured with a Gouy balance at room temperature.

Preparation of Complexes

$\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{L})_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$

To a solution of 2.32 g of $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 50 ml of water is added slowly a solution containing 3.76 g violuric or thiovioluric acid and excess of sodium bicarbonate in 200 ml of water. Stream of air is passed for about 2 hours through the solution. The resulting orange-red solution is filtered, acidified (*pH* ~ 3) and allowed to crystallize overnight. The reddish needle-shaped crystals are washed with cold water and dried in air. Yield 2.5 g.

$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6][\text{Co}(\text{HL})_3] \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$

To a orange-red solution of above complex (before acidification) is added slowly a hot solution (60°) of 2.2 g of $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6\text{Cl}_3$ in water with continuous stirring. After cooling the microcrystalline

Experimental

Violuric acid (VA) was procured from Eastman Kodak (USA) and thiovioluric acid (TVA) was

precipitate is filtered, washed with water, ethanol and dried in the air.

An ethanolic solution of trioctyl methylammonium chloride (1.6 g in 80 ml) is slowly added with vigorous stirring to a hot (60°) solution of 1g of $Co(H_2L)_3 \cdot 5H_2O$ in 500 ml of water. The amorphous precipitate is repeatedly washed with water, and ether and recrystallized from methanol-water (2 : 1) mixture.

Saturated solution (20 ml) of CsCl is added to 30 ml solution containing 0.75 g of $Co(H_2L)_3 \cdot 5H_2O$ and 0.15 g of sodium bicarbonate. The resulting solution is left to crystallize for several hours. The crystals are filtered, washed with very few ml of cold water (4°) and dried in the air.

Results and Discussion

Results of analysis (Table 1) confirm the formula assigned to various complexes. Complexes of type $Co(H_2L)_3 \cdot 5H_2O$ are diamagnetic which shows them to be of low spin type^{5,6,11}. They are stable in air but on keeping them in a calcium chloride desiccator a trihydrate is obtained which have a similar crystal shape. Thermogravimetric analysis, however reveals that dehydration takes place in two well defined steps

The anhydrous complexes are stable up to 250° and an exothermic decomposition takes place thereafter.

The pentahydrates are slightly water soluble (~10⁻³ mol/l) and aqueous solutions are acidic in nature. Solubility increases in hot water and in alkaline medium. They are dissolved instantaneously in sodium bicarbonate solution with the liberation of carbon dioxide, thus indicating the acidic nature of complexes.

Conductometric and potentiometric titrations with 0.1M sodium hydroxide show that they behave as triprotic acid. The potentiometric titration curve has been found to have a well defined inflection at pH~8 when 3 moles of alkali per mole of complex is added. This indicates the formation of species $[Co(HL)_3]^{3-}$

The pH of initial solution as the conductivity decreases (which the NaOH addition produces initially) indicates that aqueous solutions of $[Co(H_2L)_3]$ are extensively dissociated as follows.

However the stepwise deprotonation equilibria are overlapped because no discontinuity in the potentiometric curve at molar ratios 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 is noticed. Therefore they have been characterised by the determination of acidity constants of $Co(H_2L)_3$. Global (association) constants β_1 have been calculated by the extrapolation method of Rossotti and Rossotti⁹. The values along with that of acidity constants are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—GLOBAL (ASSOCIATION) AND ACIDITY CONSTANTS OF COMPLEXES AT 25±1° AND IONIC STRENGTH 0.5M KCl

Complex	$\beta_1 \times 10^5$	$\beta_2 \times 10^9$	$\beta_3 \times 10^{13}$	$K_{a_1} \times 10^{-4}$	$K_{a_2} \times 10^{-5}$	$K_{a_3} \times 10^{-6}$
$Co(H_2VA)_3$	1.60	3.55	9.00	3.90	4.50	6.20
$Co(H_2TVA)_3$	1.65	3.60	9.08	3.85	4.46	6.16

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Complex	Found (calculated)%			
	Co	C	H	N
$Co(H_2VA)_3 \cdot 5H_2O$	9.50(9.55)	23.5(23.33)	2.50(2.60)	20.50(20.41)
$Co(H_2TVA)_3 \cdot 5H_2O$	9.45(9.52)	22.25(23.30)	2.47(2.55)	20.30(20.35)
$[(C_8H_{17})_3(CH_3)_2N]_2[Co(H_2VA)(HVA)_2]$	4.50(4.67)	59.70(60.00)	9.00(8.90)	12.20(12.22)
$[(C_8H_{17})_3(CH_3)_2N]_2[Co(H_2TVA)(HTVA)_2]$	4.45(4.65)	59.95(59.85)	9.00(8.85)	12.30(12.18)
$[Co(NH_3)_6][Co(HVA)_2] \cdot 6H_2O$	14.70(14.86)	18.20(18.15)	4.0(4.16)	23.70(23.80)
$[Co(NH_3)_6][Co(HTVA)_2] \cdot 6H_2O$	14.72(14.80)	18.00(18.10)	3.95(4.12)	23.84(23.74)
$Cs[Co(H_2VA)_2(HVA)] \cdot 3H_2O$	8.30(8.26)	20.30(20.2)	1.50(1.54)	17.80(17.60)
$Cs[Co(H_2TVA)_2(HTVA)] \cdot 3H_2O$	8.32(8.22)	20.35(20.15)	1.50(1.52)	17.50(17.54)

VA = Violuric acid.

TVA = Thiovioluric acid.

The above studies reveal that coordination to Co(III) does a strong acidity increase of the violurate or thioviolurate ligand H_2L^- , that loses a second proton easily whereas the free ligand only is additionally deprotonated in very basic medium ($K_{a_2} \sim 10^{-10}$). Similar behaviour¹⁰ is observed for isoelectronic $[Ru(H_2VA)_3]^-$.

Various equilibrium species have been isolated by selective precipitation with counter ions. $[Co(H_2L)(HL)_2]^{2-}$ can be precipitated, even at pH values (~ 3) where its equilibrium concentration is negligible, with $(C_8H_{17})_3(CH_3)N^+$ ion.

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